

DETERMINED PATHOGENS IN URINARY TRACT INFECTIONS IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA**Hiora Igor,***Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
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Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

Urinary tract infections (UTIs), the second most common infectious disease, are recognized as a major problem associated with health systems worldwide[1]. The problem with UTIs is two-dimensional. Economically, hospitalization for a primary diagnosis of UTI costs \$2.8 billion annually,[31] in addition to 1 million emergency department visits and 7 million office visits.[4] On the other hand, there are a very large number of patients with UTIs who need to be seen by a large number of physicians and specialists, requiring a large number of human resources in the public health system.

Keywords: Kidney function, Chronic kidney disease, Urinary Tract infections, Chronic Pyelonephritis.

Introduction

Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are recognised as a major problem associated with health systems worldwide and rank second (after VRI) in the incidence of infectious diseases. The annual incidence of diagnosed UTIs in the United States exceeds 10% of women and 3% of men, and more than 60% of women will be diagnosed with a UTI in their lifetime. Urinary tract infections are a major morbidity factor for the population, as 60% of women who have been cured of a UTI will relapse in the following year. Economically, in the United States, hospitalization for a primary diagnosis of UTI costs \$2.8 billion annually [31], in addition to 1 million emergency department visits and 7 million office visits [4]. The development of urinary tract infection in hospitalized patients prolongs the length of time patients are unable to work and complicates their care. In addition, urosepsis accounts for 25% of all adult sepsis cases and is associated with an overall mortality rate of 20-40%. [5]

An important issue in the treatment of complicated and uncomplicated urinary tract infections is antibiotic resistance. Thus, there is a high frequency of resistance of community-acquired E. coli strains to Ampicillin and Co-trimoxazole.

Research material and methods

The research in the framework of the thesis was carried out on a group of 37 patients, who were hospitalized in the Hospital "St. Trinity" nephrology department. During the year 2022 July-October data from the hospital archive was analyzed, from which the observation files of 36 patients with the diagnosis of urinary tract infections were selected.

The patients were under investigation and treatment in the above ward in the years 2010-2022. To record and process more objective information for each patient included in the study, the following patient information was entered into an Excel table: first name, last name, age, gender, diagnosis, pathogen, antibiogram.

Inclusion criteria:

Positive uroculture $\geq 10^5$ CFU/ml;
A distinct bacterial strain on uroculture;
Female and male patients;
Age ≥ 18 years.

Exclusion criteria:

Uroculture $< 10^5$ CFU/ml;
Multiple bacterial strain on uroculture;
Presence of a urological catheter.

Figure 4. Breakdown of patients by pathogen category

According to the results (Figure 4) Escherichia coli was the most common etiologic agent of UTI (46%), followed by Enterococcus Faecalis (32%), Klebsiela pneumonia (8%), Pseudomonas aeruginosa (5%), Staphylococcus hemoliticus (6%) and Candida Crusei (5%).

According to the results of this graph(Fig. 4), E. coli and Enterococcus faecalis together account for 78% of the infectious agents found in urinary tract infections, which proves that when prescribing empirical treatment, emphasis should be placed on drugs that have proven efficacy against E. coli and Enterococcus Faecalis.

Fig 7. Duration of hospitalisation according to pathogen.

The most favourable infectious agent is E. coli, which has an average duration of treatment of 7.28 days, followed by Enterococcus faecalis, with an average duration of 8.33 days.

Klebsiela Pneumonia, with a duration of 13.5 days, is third by duration.

The most serious urinary tract infections are Pseudomonas Aeruginosa and Staphylococcus haemolyticus with an average duration of 14 and 15.6 days.

Figure 8. Rate of infectious agent involvement depending on clinical diagnosis.

After highlighting the clinical diagnosis, we investigated which infectious agents frequently infect patients, depending on the clinical diagnosis. It showed that patients with chronic pyelonephritis are most commonly infected with Gram-negative *E. coli* (70%) and in 30% of cases *Enterococcus faecalis*.

The patients with polycystic kidney disease in this study were all infected with Gram-negative *E. coli*.

Glomerulonephritis patients in the study had *Klebsiela Pneumonia* in 50% of cases and *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* in 50% of cases. I attribute this to their frequent hospitalizations due to exacerbation of underlying disease or dialysis treatments during which they infected with nosocomial infections.

Patients with acute pyelonephritis were infected with *E. coli* in 70% of cases. *Coli* and 30% were infected with *Enterococcus faecalis*.

Patients diagnosed with BCR were all infected with *Klebsiela Pneumonia*. Patients diagnosed with Acute Nephrotic Insufficiency were infected with *Enterococcus Faecalis* in 100% of cases.

Discussion:

E. coli and *Enterococcus faecalis* together account for 78% of infectious agents found in urinary tract infections, which proves that when prescribing empirical treatment, emphasis should be placed on drugs that have proven efficacy against *E. coli* and *Enterococcus faecalis*.

Conclusions:

1. The most common pathogen causing UTI encountered in St. Trinity Hospital nephrology department is Gram-negative bacillus *E. Coli*, followed by *Enterococcus* and, less frequently, nosocomial infections caused by *Klebsiela Pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus Aureus* and *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*.

2. Infectious agents with the best prognosis are *E. Coli* and *Enterococcus Faecalis*, with the shortest duration of treatment (7.28 and 8.33 days), occurring in

equal proportions in both men and women and most often affecting the third age group (>55 years).

3. The most unfavourable, which are harder to treat and have a hospitalisation duration of 14 and 15.5 days are *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus Aureus*, which infect people with weakened immune systems and have a longer duration of disease progression.

4. For the treatment of urinary tract infections we use antibiotics depending on the pathogen

-For *E. Coli* we recommend for treatment the group of cephalosporins, Meropenem, Imipinem, Gentamicin, Amikacin, Chloramphenicol, Cotrimaxozol, Nitrofurantion.

-*Enterococcus Faecalis* (Ampicillin, Amoxicillin, Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid, Imipinem, Linezolid, Ciprofloxacin, Vancomycin, Nitrofurantion).

-*Candida* (Ketoconazole, Miconazole, Itraconazole)

-*Staphylococcus haemolyticus* (Amikacin, Linezolid, Vancomycin)

-*Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (Meropenem, Imipinem in high doses)

References

- Behzadi P. Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and Fimbrial Adhesins Virulome. *Urinary Tract Infection—The Result of the Strength of the Pathogen, or the Weakness of the Host*. Croatia: InTech; 2018. pp. 65-83
- Chibelea, C.B.; Petca, R.-C.; Mareş, C.; Popescu, R.-I.; Enikő, B.; Mehedințu, C.; Petca, A. A clinical perspective on the antimicrobial resistance spectrum of uropathogens in a Romanian male population. *Microorganisms* 2020, 8, 848
- Chu CM, Lowder JL. Diagnosis and treatment of urinary tract infections across age groups. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2018; 219: 40–51

4. Chu, C.M.; Lowder, J.L. Diagnosis and treatment of urinary tract infections across age groups. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* 2018, 219, 40–51. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
5. Foxman B. Epidemiology of urinary tract infections: incidence, morbidity, and economic costs, *Am J Med*, 2012, vol. 113 (pg. 5-13]
6. Flores-Mireles, A.L.; Walker, J.N.; Caparon, M.; Hultgren, S.J. Urinary tract infections: Epidemiology, mechanisms of infection and treatment options. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 2015, 13, 269–284
7. Foxman B, Barlow R, D'Arcy H, Gillespie B & Sobel JD Urinary tract infection: self-reported incidence and associated costs. *Ann Epidemiol* 10, 509–515 (2000). [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
8. Foxman B & Brown P Epidemiology of urinary tract infections: transmission and risk factors, incidence, and costs. *Infect Dis Clin North Am* 17, 227–241 (2013). [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
9. Foxman B, Gillespie B, Koopman J, et al. Risk factors for second urinary tract infection among college women. *Am J Epidemiol* 2010
10. Foxman B. The epidemiology of urinary tract infection. *Nature Reviews Urology.* 2010;7(12):653
11. François M, Hanslik T, Dervaux B, Le Strat Y, Souty C, Vaux S, et al. The economic burden of urinary tract infections in women visiting general practices in France: A cross-sectional survey. *BMC Health Services Research.* 2016;16(1):365
12. Gupta, K, Hooton TM, Roberts PL et al. Short-course nitrofurantoin for the treatment of acute uncomplicated cystitis in women. *Arch Intern Med* 2007 Nov;167(20):2207–12.
13. Gupta K, Stamm WE. Outcomes associated with trimethoprim/sulphamethoxazole (TMP/SMX) therapy in TMP/SMX resistant community-acquired UTI. *Int J Antimicrob Agents* 2002 Jun;19(6):554–6.
14. Health Promotion Board Singapore. Urinary tract infection. [Accessed February 1 2016].
15. Jepson RG, Craig JC. Cranberries for preventing urinary tract infections. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews.* 2008;1:1-26
16. Lo E, et al. Strategies to prevent catheter-associated urinary tract infections in acute care hospitals: 2014 update. *Infect Control Hosp Epidemiol.* 2014;35:464–479. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
17. Medina, M.; Castillo-Pino, E. An introduction to the epidemiology and burden of urinary tract infections. *Ther. Adv. Urol.* 2019, 11, 1756287219832172.
18. Rafalsky V, Andreeva I, Rjabkova E. Quinolones for uncomplicated acute cystitis in women. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* 2006 Jul 19;3:CD003597
19. Schmiemann G, Kniehl E, Gebhardt K, et al. The diagnosis of urinary tract infection: a systematic review. *Dtsch Arztebl Int* 2010; 107: 361–367.
20. Scholes D et al. Risk factors for recurrent urinary tract infection in young women. *J Infect Dis* 182, 1177–1182, doi: 10.1086/315827 (2000).
21. Simmering JE, Tang F, Cavanaugh JE, Polgreen LA & Polgreen PM The Increase in Hospitalizations for Urinary Tract Infections and the Associated Costs in the United States, 1998-2011. *Open Forum Infect Dis* 4, ofw281, doi: 10.1093/ofid/ofw281 (2017).
22. Stamm WE, Norrby SR. Urinary tract infections: disease panorama and challenges. *J Infect Dis* 2011;183(Suppl 1):S1–4.
23. Wagenlehner FM et al. Diagnosis and management for urosepsis. *Int J Urol* 20, 963–970, doi: 10.1111/iju.12200 (2013).